

CONSTRUCTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF AN ACHIEVEMENT TEST OF ECONOMICS FOR ELEVENTH GRADE STUDENTS

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Abstract

This paper highlights the process of development and standardization of achievement test in Economics for Class 11th, Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi. Initially a preliminary draft of criterion referenced test consisting of 110 items was prepared. Five subject experts were personally requested to reflect their opinion upon every statement. After getting feedback from themselves; some items were modified and 10 items were identified as dead distracters. A total of 100 test items were preserved for the final draft of Criterion Referenced Test in Economics. The tryout of criterion referenced test was taken to a sample of 50 students of class 11th studying in Shri Guru Harkrishan Public School, GT road, Amritsar. A criteria of Kelley (1939) method was opted for item analysis i.e. to find out Difficulty Value (DV) and Discrimination Power (DP) of the criterion referenced test. After try out and item analysis of criterion reference test, 85 items were retained for the first draft of achievement test in Economics. Popham (1975) suggested less sophisticated but more meaningful reliability measures to be employed when marked range restrictions are present. For reliability measures he had suggested few techniques. The investigator selected the one in which percentage of scores of students were to be calculated on two different occasions. The development of achievement test passed through three stages: (i) first draft of achievement test (ii) second draft of achievement test (iii) final draft of achievement test. So, the first draft of achievement test consisted of 85 items. After try out of first draft of achievement test to 100 students of class 11th studying in Ajanta Public School, Basant Avenue, Amritsar, the same criteria was adopted for item analysis i.e. to find out Difficulty Value (DV) and Discrimination Power (DP) for the first draft of Achievement Test. A total of 65 items were remained for the second draft of achievement test in English. After try out upon students of class 11th studying in Shri Guru Harkrishan Public School, D-Block, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar, the above same criteria was adopted for item analysis for the second draft of achievement test in Economics. After item analysis of second draft of achievement test in Economics, a total of 50 items were remained left for the final draft of achievement test in Economics. The test-retest reliability of the measure of achievement test was found to be 0.71. The Validity was established by content validity method.

Keywords: Construction, Standardization, Criterion Referenced Test, Achievement test in Economics

Introduction

The process of teaching and learning activities is regulated by achievement tests. They support the assessment of instructional effectiveness. Achievement exams record the level of learning or achievement following instructions and are past and present oriented. Any test that gauges a person's accomplishments or attainments following a time of learning is an achievement test, according to Dowine and Heath (1974). It can also be viewed as an example or gauge of a student's knowledge obtained at a specific moment in time. As a result,

the purpose of accomplishment assessments is to gauge the knowledge and skills that are acquired by students from formal as well as informal training. These are used to assess study plans, the effectiveness of teachers and their methods.

Achievement tests are different from intelligence or aptitude tests in that the former assess the amount and quality of knowledge acquired in a subject or set of subjects following a specific amount of instruction, while the latter assess a student's intrinsic ability to achieve or succeed without the need for learning. Achievement tests were categorized by Lindeman (1967) into the following groups: (i) Teacher Made Tests (ii) Standardized Tests

(i) Assessments created by teachers are often used to gauge how well pupils are doing in class. These are typically more narrowly focused and represent the material covered in a given unit or course. The test that the teacher created is designed to gauge students' performance and goals for them once they have finished the course's set of learning assignments. It appears that applying the methods and accumulated experience of experienced teachers can significantly improve the preparation for local classroom exams. To guarantee high quality test results and successfully assess students' learning, teachers must adhere to strict rules while creating their own assessments in the classroom.

(ii) On the other hand the standardized tests are distinct test types that differ from the final exam a high school teacher may create for his subject. Standardized refers only to the fact that all test takers get the same amount of time and view identical or almost identical questions. Standardized also refers to extremely meticulous scoring, thus test results are independent of the individual scoring the item. These exams are commonly utilized because, in general, they have proven to be an effective means of gathering data regarding people's knowledge and abilities.

(iii) These are legitimate in that they frequently offer pertinent and helpful information for determining one's level of success potential and mastery of a body of knowledge and abilities. As a result, a standardized test is one that is given and graded consistently. The tests are made to be administered and scored in a predetermined, standard manner with consistent questions, conditions for administering, scoring procedures and interpretations.

❖ **Development and Standardization of Criterion Referenced Test in Economics**

The term criterion referenced test was first used by Glaser in 1963. As per Emrick (1971), "Criterion referenced test is a gathering of things described by comparable trouble as well as balance in shape and substance". According to Ivens (1970), "The term criterion-referenced test has been characterized in connection to behavioral goals. A criterion referenced test is a test made out of things keyed to an arrangement of behavioral objectives". The test with criteria referenced aims to capture a representation of the specific knowledge and abilities that each student can demonstrate. This information is useful for setting both individual and group guidelines. Then, in tests that are criterion referenced, each examinee's performance is compared to a predefined set of criteria or a benchmark. Determining whether the contender has demonstrated mastery of a particular skill or group of skills is the aim of these assessments. The accompanying advancements such as (1) content specification, (2) instructional objective specification, and (3) development and standardization of the criterion referenced test were included in the criterion referenced test below is a thorough description of the criteria-referenced exam ventures:

1. Content Specification: The investigator chose four units of economics from the Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi, and approved syllabus for the 11th class for the current investigation. This was done because the economics curriculum was the researcher's area of expertise. To get their opinions on certain themes chosen from the syllabus, the economics teachers were consulted. The details of the selected content have been given in table-1:

Table-1: Unit wise details of the selected content in economics

No.	Units
1.	<i>Collection, Organization and Presentation of Data:</i> Introduction, Sources of Data, Sampling, Frequency Distribution
2.	<i>Statistical Tools and Interpretation:</i> Measures of Central Tendency, Measures of Dispersion, Correlation
3.	<i>Consumer's Equilibrium and Demand:</i> Utility, Marginal Utility, Demand, Law of Demand, Elasticity of Demand
4.	<i>Producer Behavior and Supply:</i> Concept of Production Function, Concept of Cost, Concept of Revenue

Table-1 shows that the content selected from the four units prescribed for class XI economics student's affiliated to Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi.

2. Specification of Instructional Objectives: The test's objectives must be established before it can be built. The exam should receive special attention since it needs to be able to accurately gauge how well educational goals can be met. The exam should be designed to highlight the extent to which the curriculum that the kid has been taught has helped to attain the goals of changing their behavior (Sahu, 2007). In order to assist the investigator develops the instructional program, the material was analyzed and objectives were established for each topic. This made the compilation of the statement of instructional objectives a crucial step in the instructional system design process. The learning of every topic was addressed by the objectives. It was determined which educational materials fell into the knowledge, comprehension, and application categories of the objectives. The statement of instructional objectives for each topic has been presented in table-2.

Table-2: Unit wise distribution of instructional objectives

Units	Instructional Objectives		
		<i>After the instructions are over every student in their own words will able to</i>	
Collection, Organization and Presentation of Data	1.1	understand the concept of collection of data and its various sources	
	1.2	understand the difference between different sources of data collection	
	1.3	develop the skill to collect data in primary sources.	
	1.4	use secondary sources of data for their problem under investigation	
	1.5	understand the difference between primary and secondary sources of data.	
	1.6	Provide information with regard to various methods of primary data collection.	
	1.7	provide information with regard to various methods of secondary data collection	
	1.8	develop skill to choose which method is appropriate in different situation	
	1.9	understand the concept of sampling	
	1.10	understand the different methods of sampling	
	1.11	develop skill to choose which method is appropriate in different situation and how to apply that method	
	1.12	know about frequency distribution	
	1.13	know about frequency distribution	

	1.14	know about different types of frequency diagrams
	1.15	develop skill to choose which type of frequency diagrams is to be used according to situation
Statistical Tools and Interpretation	2.1	know about meaning of statistical tools
	2.2	understand about measures of central tendency
	2.3	understand the concept of arithmetic mean
	2.4	know where to use mean in real life situations
	2.5	understand the concept of median
	2.6	understand the uses of median
	2.7	understand difference between mean and median
	2.8	understand the concept of mode
	2.9	understand the relation between mean, median and mode
	2.10	understand the concept of dispersion
	2.11	enable the students to know about various measures of dispersion
	2.12	understand the uses of different measures of dispersion in real life
	2.13	develop the skill to choose best method of dispersion
	2.14	understand the concept of correlation
	2.15	enable them to understand types of correlation
	2.16	enable them to understand methods of finding correlation
	2.17	understand the concept of Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation
	2.18	know about the uses of Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation in real life
	2.19	understand the concept of Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient
	2.20	choose best method according to situation
Consumer's Equilibrium and Demand	3.1	understand the concept of utility
	3.2	understand the different concepts like initial utility, marginal utility and total utility.
	3.3	differentiate features of utility
	3.4	understand the relationship between total utility and marginal utility.
	3.5	understand the concept of consumer's equilibrium
	3.6	draw consumer equilibrium point on graph
	3.7	give examples of consumer's equilibrium from real market situation
	3.8	understand the concept of demand
	3.9	quote examples of demand from real life
	3.10	understand the concept of law of demand
	3.11	illustrate law of demand with the help of examples
	3.12	draw law of demand graphically
	3.13	understand concept of elasticity of demand
	3.14	know about different types of elasticity of demand
Producer Behavior and Supply	4.1	understand concept of production function
	4.2	understand long run and short run production function
	4.3	understand the practical applicability of production function
	4.4	know the concept of cost
	4.5	understand the concepts of fixed cost and variable cost
	4.6	understand the concept of marginal cost and average cost
	4.7	understand relationship between average, marginal and total cost
	4.8	understand the concept of revenue
	4.9	understand about total revenue, marginal revenue and average revenue
	4.10	understand relation between total revenue, marginal revenue and average

	revenue
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According to table-2, four units were chosen from the class 11th economics syllabus offered by the Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi. The chosen economics subject served as the basis for the 59 teaching goals.

3. Development and Standardization of the Criterion Referenced Test

A test designed to enable the assessment of an examinee's proficiency in relation to a clearly defined behavior domain is known as a criterion-referenced test (Popham, 1975). In the hierarchical learning hierarchy, every behavior domain is essential to achieving a certain goal. An exam that is criterion referenced is designed to evaluate how well pupils have mastered each learning hierarchy target. A well-designed criteria reference test entails the following steps: (i) Planning of the test (ii) Writing and Editing of test items (iii) Try out and Item analysis and (iv) Evaluation. Below is a description of the construction phase:

(i) *Planning of the Test:* It was determined that the test was intended for the students between the age group of 13 to 18 after carefully reviewing the Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi, mandated syllabus for XI economics students. Major course instructional behavioral objectives and the primary material area were determined. For this study, fifteen economics-based courses from class XI were chosen. Keeping in mind the aims and content of the instructional material, the investigator created three different sorts of questions multiple choice, fill in the blank, and true/false. For the present test, a blue print with three dimensions viz. knowledge, understanding and comprehension of content were prepared as shown in table-3:

Table-3: Specification of the preliminary draft of criterion referenced test in economics

No	Units	Objectives	Type of Test Items									Total
			Knowledge			Understanding			Comprehension			
			F	TF	MC	F	TF	MC	F	TF	MC	
1.	Collection, Organization and Presentation of Data	15	-	1	5	1	1	7	1	1	7	24
2.	Statistical Tools and Interpretation	20	1	1	7	-	1	9	1	-	8	28
3.	Consumer's Equilibrium and Demand	14	1	-	6	-	1	8	1	1	5	24
4.	Producer Behavior and Supply	10	2	1	10	-	1	10	1	1	10	34
	Total	59	4	4	27	2	5	33	4	3	28	110

Note: F Signifies Fill in the Blanks, T/F Signifies True/ False and MC Signifies Multiple Choices

Table-3 demonstrates that there were 15 planned objectives for the first unit, 20 prepared objectives for the second unit, 14 prepared objectives for the third unit, and 10 prepared objectives for the fourth unit. Three different kinds of questions were prepared: multiple choice, true-false, and fill-in-the-blank. Therefore, for the initial draft of the criterion-referenced test, 110 items in total and 59 objectives were framed.

(ii) *Writing and Editing of Test Items:* Simple language was employed when drafting the pieces. Numerical quantities and alphabetical order of options were provided. We steered clear of textbook terminology. In order to pique students' interest, questions with a numerical component and questions requiring thinking were also added. We avoided using words like

seldom, never, and sometimes. Following consideration of the aforementioned points, the investigator created an initial draft of a 110 item criteria test. Experts in economics who work in universities and schools were given this exam to review for language and content, to look for a relationship between the test item's aims and the subject it and to recommend additional questions.

The investigator individually asked each of the five experts to consider each statement carefully and to determine how each statement came closest to the stated objectives. The investigator and her supervisor spent multiple meetings deliberating over the expert opinions about the statements. Individual discussions were done with subject-matter experts, the teachers. After getting feedback from subject experts some items were modified and 10 items i.e. 9, 14, 16, 35, 52, 61, 79, 84, 95 and 106 were identified as dead distracters. The 100 test items were preserved for the final draft of the criterion referenced test.

(iii) *Try-Out and Item Analysis:* The final draft of criterion referenced test was administered to a sample of 50 students drawn from 11th class of Shri Guru Harkrishan Public School, GT road, Amritsar who had already studied the selected content and just completed their X class. Although there was no time constraint set, it was discovered that most students finished the test in around 1:15 minutes. The experts' and students' observations were recorded and taken into account when the test was revised. It should be noted that, in contrast to other assessments, the criterion referenced test describes the students' entry level and the degree to which they have mastered the predetermined set of terminal behavior. The scoring key was used to assess the answer sheets. Item analysis was initiated following the scoring. Item analysis is the process of determining if test items are adequate by examining how each examinee responds to each item.

(iv) *Evaluation:* The main purpose of the test's item analysis is to find any ambiguities, bits of information, ineffective distracters, and specific defects that might have gone unnoticed during test construction. Additionally, it produces two other types of data: specifically, records of things like the discrimination index and difficulty value. The relevant response sheets were evaluated and scored in a sliding order. The item analysis criteria of Kelley (1939) were applied in order to determine the discrimination power and difficulty value. The following method was used to calculate the discrimination index and difficulty value such as:

- (a) The answer sheets of the students were arranged in descending order.
- (b) The top 27 % cases formed the upper group and bottom 27 % formed the lower group.
- (c) After that the correct responses for each item in both the groups were calculated.

There are 13 pupils in each group. Because of this, the difficulty value and discriminating power were determined using the 26 students who made up those subgroups. For calculating difficulty value and discrimination power, the following formulas were used:

$$\text{Difficulty Value} = \frac{R_U + R_L}{N} \qquad \text{Discriminating Power} = \frac{R_U - R_L}{N/2}$$

Where:

R_U = Number of correct responses in upper group

R_L = Number of correct responses in lower group

N = Total number of students in both the groups

Table-4: Distribution of the difficulty value and discriminating power of items of the final draft of criterion referenced test in economics

Item No.	R_U	R_L	DV	DP	Remarks
1	10	07	0.69	0.42	A

Item No.	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
2	07	03	0.38	0.46	A
3	11	04	0.58	0.54	A
4	08	04	0.46	0.46	A
5	12	03	0.58	0.69	A
6	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
7	12	06	0.69	0.46	A
8	12	07	0.73	0.23	A
9	11	08	0.73	0.23	A
10	10	02	0.46	0.62	A
11	12	10	0.85	0.15	R
12	10	03	0.50	0.54	A
13	06	01	0.26	0.46	A
14	06	02	0.31	0.31	A
15	10	05	0.57	0.38	A
16	13	11	0.92	0.15	R
17	06	02	0.31	0.31	A
18	02	01	0.12	0.08	R
19	11	05	0.61	0.46	A
20	05	02	0.26	0.15	R
21	11	05	0.61	0.46	A
22	11	09	0.77	0.15	R
23	08	04	0.46	0.31	A
24	12	03	0.58	0.69	A
25	11	02	0.50	0.69	A
26	11	06	0.65	0.38	A
27	10	03	0.50	0.54	A
28	09	05	0.54	0.28	A
29	07	02	0.35	0.38	A
30	11	04	0.57	0.53	A
31	07	04	0.35	0.38	A
32	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
33	06	03	0.34	0.23	A
34	11	01	0.46	0.75	A
35	13	06	0.73	0.53	A
36	06	01	0.26	0.38	A
37	10	05	0.58	0.38	A
38	12	06	0.69	0.46	A
39	06	02	0.31	0.31	A
40	11	09	0.77	0.15	R
41	11	01	0.46	0.75	A
42	10	04	0.54	0.46	A
43	09	03	0.46	0.46	A
44	08	01	0.34	0.53	A
45	09	03	0.46	0.46	A
46	02	00	0.08	0.15	R
47	08	03	0.42	0.38	A
48	10	05	0.58	0.38	A

Item No.	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
49	08	04	0.46	0.28	A
50	12	06	0.69	0.46	A
51	05	02	0.27	0.15	R
52	11	04	0.58	0.54	A
53	09	02	0.42	0.54	A
54	02	00	0.08	0.15	R
55	07	04	0.50	0.23	A
56	11	04	0.58	0.54	A
57	05	02	0.85	0.15	R
58	08	03	0.42	0.38	A
59	08	05	0.50	0.23	A
60	06	03	0.34	0.23	A
61	09	06	0.58	0.23	A
62	11	09	0.62	0.24	A
63	09	06	0.58	0.23	A
64	12	07	0.73	0.38	A
65	08	05	0.50	0.23	A
66	09	03	0.46	0.15	R
67	09	02	0.42	0.54	A
68	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
69	08	05	0.50	0.23	A
70	12	07	0.73	0.45	A
71	07	01	0.31	0.46	A
72	10	02	0.46	0.62	A
73	12	10	0.85	0.15	R
74	09	06	0.58	0.23	A
75	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
76	01	00	0.04	0.08	R
77	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
78	08	04	0.46	0.31	A
79	10	04	0.54	0.46	A
80	12	04	0.62	0.62	A
81	08	02	0.38	0.46	A
82	09	06	0.58	0.32	A
83	12	03	0.58	0.69	A
84	05	02	0.27	0.23	A
85	10	01	0.42	0.69	A
86	06	02	0.30	0.31	A
87	03	01	0.15	0.15	R
88	05	02	0.27	0.31	A
89	06	01	0.27	0.38	A
90	09	05	0.54	0.31	A
91	08	00	0.31	0.62	A
92	08	01	0.35	0.62	A
93	07	02	0.35	0.38	A
94	10	04	0.54	0.46	A
95	10	02	0.46	0.62	A

Item No.	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
96	11	05	0.62	0.46	A
97	09	06	0.58	0.30	A
98	08	02	0.15	0.09	R
99	08	04	0.46	0.31	A
100	07	02	0.35	0.38	A

Note: Here 'A' stands for Accepted items and 'R' stands for Rejected items

The final draft of the criterion referenced test had a discriminating power that ranged from 0.09 to 0.75, as Table 4 illustrates. When the discrimination value is 0.40 or above, the items are deemed to be extremely good and do not require adjustment. Acknowledge and carefully consider how to improve the item if the discrimination value falls between 0.30 and 0.39. When an item's discrimination value is between 0.20 to 0.29 it declares as marginal item and can be used after improvement; items with a discrimination value of 0.19 or less are rejected.

The above table demonstrates that 45 items were deemed very good if their discriminating power was more than 0.40, 25 items were deemed considerably good if their discriminating power was between 0.30 to 0.39, 15 items were deemed marginal if their discriminating power ranges between 0.20 to 0.29, and 15 items were likely to be eliminated if their discriminating power below 0.19. Selecting items with an appropriate difficulty level was the primary motivation behind measuring item difficulty. The Ebel (1966) criteria are applied, which state that items with difficulty levels above 0.75 and below 0.25 were disqualified because they were, respectively, extremely easy and extremely tough. The accomplishment test accepted the items with difficulty values ranging from 0.25 to 0.75 as such. Nonetheless, the first draft's item difficulty levels varied from 0.04 to 0.92. Six of the items in the above table have tough values greater than 0.75, meaning they are easy objects.

There were one 100 items in the final draft of the criterion referenced test. These products underwent analysis and evaluation in order to improve their quality. Distracters that are not close to the appropriate reaction location need to be updated or adjusted. By making the distracters that oppose the correct answer less appealing, it is possible to prevent the students from becoming more interested in them than in the correct response. The distribution of weak distracters of the final draft of criterion referenced test has been given in the table 5.

Table-5: Distribution of distracters competing with correct response and weak distracter of the final draft of criterion referenced test in economics

No	Form of Response	Item Number	f
1.	Distracters Competing with Correct Response	1, 7, 8, 9, 26, 35, 38, 50, 64,70	10
2.	Weak Distracters	11,16, 18, 20, 22, 40, 46, 51, 54, 57, 66, 73, 76, 87, 98	15

Table-5 demonstrates that, of the 100 total questions, 10 were distracters that competed with the right answer; these items were rewritten with this in mind. 15 items that were weak distracters were removed from the final draft of the test that was criteria referenced. As a result, for the accomplishment test's initial draft, the final 85 items were kept. The selected and rejected items of the test after calculation of difficulty value and discriminating power for the first draft of achievement test are given below in table-6.

Table-6: Selected and rejected items for the first draft of achievement test

No	f	Item Number	Remarks
1.	85	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 47, 48, 49, 50, 52, 53, 55, 56, 58, 59, 60, 61, 63, 64, 65, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 74, 75, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 99, 100.	Selected Items
2.	15	11, 16, 18, 20, 22, 40, 46, 51, 54, 57, 66, 73, 76, 87, 98.	Rejected Items

Table-6 shows that out of total 100 items, 15 items were rejected and 85 items were retained for the first draft of achievement test in economics. Hence, there were 85 items for the first draft of achievement test.

- **Reliability:** Hambleton and Novick (1973) suggest that "the reliability of criterion-referenced tests might most appropriately be viewed from the stand point of consistency of decisions across repeated testing." According to Millman (1974), for any test including criterion-referenced tests, standardization is an essential concept. The test-retest approach was utilized in the current investigation to determine the reliability coefficient of the criterion-referenced test. The reliability study of criterion referenced test was conducted over a sample of 50 students drawn from Khalsa College International Public School, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar. The second administration of the test was carried out after two weeks. The reliability of the measures of this achievement test was found out to be 0.71. The Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation method was used to calculate the reliability of criterion referenced test. It is the ratio which express the extent to which changes in one variable are accompanied by or dependent upon changes in the second variable.
- **Validity:** The content validity was adopted by the investigator for validation of the test. The content validity of the test was established by relating the test items to the instructional objectives. Thus, 85 items were retained for the first draft of achievement test in economics.

❖ An Achievement Test in Economics

It has been recognized that achievement test is an integral and important part of educational process. It measures the extent to which a person has achieved acquired certain information of mastered certain skills, usually as a result of specific instruction, (Stanley & Hopkins, 1972). Ebel (1966) was of the view that achievement test is a sample of indicator of a student's knowledge taken at a particular point of time. An achievement test can be designed for two purposes. First, performance can be measured to provide information about the characteristics of students' present behavior. Second, achievement can be measured to provide information about the instructional treatment which produces that behavior. So from the above point of view the development of an achievement test was a crying need. Achievement test was developed from those criterion test items which showed significant response variance to measure the performance of students. It can be differentiated from the criterion test on the basis of purpose, difficulty range, normality of conditions etc. Development of an achievement test passed through three stages such as (i) first draft of achievement test (ii) second draft of achievement test (iii) final draft of achievement test. The description of all drafts achievement test is given below:

- (i) **First Draft of Achievement Test in Economics:** The first draft of achievement test was prepared on the basis of 85 test items selected after the validation of criterion referenced tests. The development of achievement test involves following steps such as (i) Planning (ii) Preparation (iii) Tryout and (iv) Evaluation. The detail description of tryout and evaluation

has been given below:

First Tryout and Evaluation: A sample of 100 students from class XI at Ajanta Public School, Basant Avenue, Amritsar were given the first draft of the achievement test, which consisted of the items from the criterion referenced test. The criteria of the Kelley (1939) method were chosen for item analysis, i.e. to find difficulty value (DV) and discriminating power (DP) of the first draft of the achievement test. The procedure has already been discussed in the previous section. Each subgroup had 27 students, and the difficulty value and discriminating power were calculated from those subgroups, totaling 54 students. The index of difficulty value (DV) and discriminating power (DP) for each item were computed as shown in table 7.

Table-7: Distribution of the difficulty value and discriminating power of items of the first draft of achievement test in economics

Item No	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
1.	27	07	0.48	0.74	A
2.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
3.	25	16	0.47	0.33	A
4.	23	16	0.72	0.26	A
5.	27	07	0.45	0.74	A
6.	26	02	0.52	0.89	A
7.	26	24	0.92	0.07	R
8.	25	16	0.75	0.33	A
9.	23	16	0.72	0.26	A
10.	24	12	0.31	0.44	A
11.	26	22	0.88	0.14	R
12.	22	16	0.70	0.22	A
13.	24	16	0.31	0.29	A
14.	22	16	0.88	0.07	R
15.	25	03	0.51	0.81	A
16.	22	08	0.37	0.51	A
17.	25	09	0.63	0.59	A
18.	25	23	0.89	0.07	R
19.	22	16	0.37	0.22	A
20.	24	16	0.74	0.29	A
21.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
22.	20	10	0.55	0.37	A
23.	22	05	0.50	0.63	A
24.	27	09	0.31	0.66	A
25.	23	09	0.59	0.51	A
26.	27	09	0.31	0.66	A
27.	22	16	0.70	0.22	A
28.	22	16	0.40	0.22	A
29.	22	05	0.41	0.63	A
30.	25	10	0.64	0.55	A
31.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
32.	22	08	0.31	0.51	A
33.	26	02	0.44	0.89	A
34.	21	02	0.42	0.70	A
35.	23	20	0.79	0.11	R

Item No	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
36.	25	23	0.88	0.07	R
37.	22	11	0.41	0.41	A
38.	24	11	0.47	0.48	A
39.	24	20	0.81	0.15	R
40.	23	15	0.70	0.29	A
41.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
42.	25	10	0.41	0.55	A
43.	24	16	0.74	0.29	A
44.	24	06	0.37	0.66	A
45.	22	07	0.53	0.55	A
46.	21	02	0.42	0.70	A
47.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
48.	23	09	0.41	0.51	A
49.	24	23	0.87	0.04	R
50.	26	02	0.37	0.89	A
51.	19	10	0.37	0.33	A
52.	24	10	0.37	0.51	A
53.	23	20	0.79	0.11	R
54.	22	07	0.31	0.55	A
55.	14	04	0.33	0.37	A
56.	16	08	0.44	0.30	A
57.	24	21	0.83	0.11	R
58.	22	16	0.70	0.22	A
59.	22	16	0.70	0.22	A
60.	22	05	0.47	0.63	A
61.	25	10	0.41	0.55	A
62.	24	22	0.85	0.07	R
63.	19	09	0.37	0.37	A
64.	16	08	0.44	0.30	A
65.	25	22	0.87	0.11	R
66.	24	11	0.64	0.48	A
67.	21	07	0.35	0.52	A
68.	23	09	0.59	0.51	A
69.	18	02	0.37	0.59	A
70.	24	06	0.31	0.66	A
71.	26	02	0.52	0.89	A
72.	18	02	0.37	0.59	A
73.	24	10	0.41	0.51	A
74.	24	19	0.79	0.18	R
75.	14	04	0.33	0.37	A
76.	19	08	0.41	0.41	A
77.	16	06	0.41	0.37	A
78.	6	04	0.18	0.07	R
79.	14	04	0.33	0.37	A
80.	24	13	0.37	0.41	A
81.	24	10	0.62	0.51	A
82.	22	05	0.39	0.63	A
83.	23	09	0.43	0.51	A
84.	22	19	0.76	0.11	R

Item No	R _U	R _L	DV	DP	Remarks
85.	22	07	0.41	0.55	A

Note: Here 'A' stands for Accepted items and 'R' stands for Rejected item

The initial draft's test items' discriminating power ranged from 0.07 to 0.89, as Table 7 demonstrates. When the discrimination value is 0.40 or above, the items are deemed to be extremely good and do not require adjustment. Acknowledge and carefully consider how to improve the item if the discrimination value falls between 0.30 and 0.39. When the discriminating value is between 0.20 and 0.29, the item may be utilized as a marginal and examined closely for improvement. When discriminating value is 0.19 or less, reject and rewrite the item (Ebel, 1965).

Table-8: Distribution of discriminating power of items of the first draft of achievement test

No	D.P.	f	Items Number	Remarks
1	above 0.40	42	1, 5, 6, 10, 15, 16, 17, 23, 24, 25, 26, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 37, 38, 42, 44, 45, 46, 48, 50, 52, 54, 60, 61, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 76, 80, 81, 82, 83, 85	Very Good Items
2	0.30 to 0.39	11	3, 8, 22, 51, 55, 56, 63, 64, 75, 77, 79	Reasonable Good Items
3	0.20 to 0.29	12	4, 9, 12, 13, 19, 20, 27, 28, 40, 43, 58, 59	Marginal Items
4	below 0.19	20	2, 7, 11, 14, 18, 21, 31, 35, 36, 39, 41, 47, 49, 53, 57, 62, 65, 74, 78, 84	Poor Items

The above table 8 shows that 20 items with a discriminating power of 0.19 or less should be eliminated, while 42 items with a discriminating power of more than 0.40 were deemed very good items, 11 items with a discriminating power between 0.30 and 0.39 were deemed considerably good items, and 12 items with a discriminating power between 0.20 and 0.29 were regarded as marginal items.

Selecting items with an appropriate difficulty level was the primary motivation behind measuring item difficulty. According to Ebel's (1966) criteria, items with difficulty levels of 0.75 and less were disqualified since they were respectively, extremely easy and extremely difficult. The achievement test accepted the items with difficulty values ranging from 0.25 to 0.75 as such. On the other hand, the original draft's item difficulty ranged from 0.18 to 0.93.

Table-9: Distribution of difficulty value of items of the first draft of achievement test

No	D.V.	f	Items Number	marks
1	above 0.75	19	2, 7, 11, 14, 18, 21, 31, 35, 36, 39, 41, 47, 49, 53, 57, 62, 65, 74, 84	Easy Items
2	0.50 to 0.75	22	4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 15, 17, 20, 22, 23, 25, 27, 30, 40, 43, 45, 58, 59, 66, 68, 71, 81.	Marginal Items
3	0.25 to 0.49	43	1, 3, 5, 10, 13, 16, 19, 24, 26, 28, 29, 32, 33, 34, 37, 38, 42, 44, 46, 48, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 60, 61, 63, 64, 67, 69, 70, 72, 73, 75, 76, 77, 79, 80, 82, 83, 85	Reasonably Good Items
4	below 0.25	01	78	Difficult Item

Table-9 shows that 19 items have a difficulty value above 0.75, indicating they are relatively easy. Conversely, only one item has a difficulty rating below 0.25, marking it as a challenging item. In total, 20 elements were removed from the initial draft. The initial draft of

the achievement test contained 85 items. To improve the quality of these items, they were carefully examined and assessed. Distracters that were not close to the correct response area were adjusted or replaced. To prevent students from being overly attracted to distracters that contradict the correct answer, these distracters were made less appealing. Table 10 presents the use of distracters competing with the correct answer, as well as the presence of inadequate or ineffective distracters in the achievement test.

Table-10: Distribution of competing distracters and weak distracters

No	Form of Response	Item Number	f
1.	Distracters competing with correct response	4, 9, 12, 13, 14, 19, 20, 31, 32, 44, 47	11
2.	Weak distracters	2, 7, 11, 14, 18, 21, 31, 35, 36, 39, 41, 47, 49, 53, 57, 62, 65, 74, 78, 84	20

Table-10 shows that out of the 85 items, 11 had distracters competing with the correct answer and were subsequently revised. Additionally, 20 items with poor distracters were removed from the original draft. Consequently, 65 items were retained for the second draft. Table 3.11 below lists the test items that were selected and rejected based on the difficulty value and discriminating power calculations for the second draft of achievement test.

Table-11: Selected and discarded items for the second draft of achievement test

No	f	Item Number	Remarks
1.	65	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 37, 38, 40, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 48, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 58, 59, 60, 61, 63, 64, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 75, 76, 77, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 85	Selected Items
2.	20	2, 7, 11, 14, 18, 21, 31, 35, 36, 39, 41, 47, 49, 53, 57, 62, 65, 74, 78, 84	Rejected Items

According to table 11, out of a total of 85 items, 20 things were deemed unacceptable and were not included in the second draft, while 65 items were considered suitable and were preserved. Therefore, there were a total of 65 items included in the second version of the accomplishment exam.

(ii) *Second Draft of Achievement Test in Economics*: The analysis of items of the test served as the foundation for the preparation of the accomplishment test's second edition. The things that were approved as is or that were changed or rewritten while keeping the difficulty level and discriminating power in mind made up the second draft.

(iii)

Tryout and Evaluation of Second Draft: The second draft consisted of those elements that were kept and updated while keeping in mind the first draft's discriminating power and difficulty value. 56 students in class 11th at Shri Guru Harkrishan Public School, D-Block, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar, took the second version of the accomplishment test. The answer sheets were scored using a key. The item analysis of the second draft was finished after the response sheets' scoring.

Table-12: Distribution of items of the difficulty value in the second draft of economics

No	D.V.	f	Item Number	Remarks
1	Above 0.75	9	5, 9, 14, 16, 19, 30, 36, 37, 65.	Easy Items

2	0.50 to 0.75	35	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 15, 17, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28, 31, 33, 34, 35, 38, 39, 40, 41, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53, 59, 61, 62, 63.	Reasonably Good Items
3	0.25 to 0.49	15	13, 18, 20, 27, 32, 42, 45, 46, 47, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 64.	Marginal Items
4	Below 0.25	6	21, 29, 43, 44, 49, 60.	Difficult Items

Table 12 reveals that six of the items have difficulty values below 0.25, which are regarded as challenging items, while nine items have difficulty values above 0.75, which indicates that these are extremely simple items. Fifteen of these elements were removed from the second draft. The index of discriminating power of each item is shown given below in table-13.

Table-13: Distribution of discriminating power of items of the second draft of achievement test in economics

No	D.P.	f	Item Number	Remarks
1	0.40 and Above	23	1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 17, 22, 23, 24, 26, 28, 34, 39, 48, 50, 52, 53, 61, 63,	Very Good Items
2	0.30 to 0.39	12	6, 15, 25, 31, 33, 35, 38, 40, 41, 51, 59, 62	Reasonably Good Items
3	0.20 to 0.29	15	13, 18, 20, 27, 32, 42, 45, 46, 47, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 64	Marginal Items
4	0.19 and Below	15	5, 9, 14, 16, 19, 21, 29, 30, 36, 37, 43, 44, 49, 60, 65,	Poor Items

(iv) *Final Draft of Achievement Test in Economics*: Table 13 indicates that 23 items were deemed very good if their discriminating power was greater than 0.40, 12 items were deemed reasonably good if their discriminating power was between 0.30 and 0.39, 15 items were deemed marginal if their discriminating power was between 0.20 and 0.29, and 15 items were deemed poor if their discriminating power was between 0.19 and less. These fifteen subpar items were removed from the revised draft. As a result, 50 elements in all were kept for the accomplishment test's final draft. The evaluation of each item's complexity and discriminating power, 50 items were kept for the achievement test's final draft. For the final draft of the accomplishment test in economics, the items with difficulty values (DV) ranging from 0.25 to 0.75 and discriminating powers (DP) ranging from 0.20 to 0.75 were kept. Both the easiest and hardest items were turned down. The accepted and rejected items of final draft of the achievement test have been given in table-14.

Table-14: Selected and rejected items for the final draft of achievement test

No	f	Item Number	Remarks
1.	50	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 17, 18, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 45, 46, 47, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 61, 62, 63, 64	Selected items
2.	15	5, 9, 14, 16, 19, 21, 29, 30, 36, 37, 43, 44, 49, 60, 65	Rejected items

Table-14 reveals that 15 items were eliminated from the second draft of the accomplishment test in economics, leaving 50 items out of 65 that were kept for the final edition. Thus, the achievement test's final draft had 50 items total 45 multiple-choice questions and 5 true false questions.

- **Administration:** The subjects were provided with comfortable chairs at a reasonable distance from one another, allowing each individual to clearly hear the voice of the analyzer. A group of ten students each received the final draft of the 50-item accomplishment test. The test's farthest point was measured to determine the normal time in which 90% of the cases could complete it; this turned out to be 40 minutes.
- **Scoring:** After being prepared, the scoring key was reviewed. The scoring key was used to help evaluate the relevant response sheets. Students received one mark for each correct response, while any incorrect responses received no negative marks. The test had a total of 50 marks.
- **Reliability:** As stated by Best and Kahn (1989), reliability is crucial to the efficacy of any data collection process. Guilford (1967) defines reliability as the percentage of true variance in the observed test scores. Anastasi (1988) views reliability as the consistency with which a set of test scores measures whatever they do measure. Fraenkel and Wallen (1993) define reliability as the consistency of the scores obtained. Given the heterogeneity of the achievement test in economics and the logical arrangement of the test items, it was determined that the two halves could not have been identical. As a result, the test-retest method of reliability was determined to be the most appropriate for the test. The test-retest method is the only practical way to prove the test's reliability, according to Mouly (1970). To estimate consistency, a respondent's response to the same question provided in two different contexts might be compared. In light of this, the test-retest approach was determined to be the superior choice because the split half approach was abandoned due to the lack of item sorting and the unmet assumptions of the unit factor test and parallel items. For the test's reliability research, a sample of 40 class XI students from Manav Public School on Anand Avenue in Amritsar was used. After a period of two weeks, the test was conducted for a second time. The product moment coefficient of correlation was computed for the two scores. It was discovered that there was a 0.81 coefficient of correlation between two test results. The test's validity is attested to by the relatively high coefficient of correlation. As a result, the accomplishment exam might be regarded as a trustworthy instrument for determining a student's economics achievement.
- **Validity:** Validity refers to the degree to which a test produces the intended findings. Examining the agreement between the answers each question item elicits and the criterion is a step in the validity process. There are four methods to determine whether a test is valid: content validity, construct validity, predictive validity, and concurrent validity. The content validity of this achievement test was assessed by a systematic study of its content to see if it adequately covers a representative sample of the behavior domain that needs to be measured. Content validity is a type of validity that is not based on statistical analysis. A group of five specialists was given the test items and a list of results to evaluate the content validity. Among the seven specialists, five have successfully solved the tests, allowing for the verification of the score key. The experts concurred with the investigator about the allocation of test items to goals, as well as the scoring of the exam. This confirmed the test's content validity.

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